

Designed synthesis of different types of heterometallic isopropoxide coordination compounds of zirconium(IV) and their characterization

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Abstract : Five interesting heterometallic coordination compounds of zirconium(IV), such as $[\text{ZrCl}_3\{\eta^4\text{-M}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Sn}$ (1), Ti (2)), $[\text{ZrCl}_2\{\eta^2\text{-Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}_2]$ (3), $[\text{ZrCl}_3\{\eta^4\text{-TiZr}(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (4) and $[\text{ZrCl}_2\{\eta^3\text{-Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}\{\eta^2\text{-Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}]$ (5), have been prepared by the reactions of ZrCl_4 with an appropriate potassium isopropoxometallate ligand in benzene. All of these complexes (1)-(5) have been satisfactorily characterized by elemental and isopropoxo group analyses, molecular weight measurements, and spectroscopic [IR, NMR (^1H , ^{27}Al , ^{119}Sn)] studies.

Keywords : Zirconium(IV) complexes, heterometallic isopropoxides, isopropoxometallates, spectral studies, isopropoxide coordination compounds.

Introduction

Heterometallic isopropoxides of zirconium(IV) are generally those in which nonaisopropoxidizirconate anion, $\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9^-$, is associated with different metal ions as a chelating ligand¹, exhibiting tetra(η^4)-, tri(η^3)- and bi(η^2)-dentate ligating modes. By contrast, zirconium(IV) centered heterometallic alkoxides are elusive and the only known examples are the derivatives of the type $\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}_2\text{ZrX}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, OPr^i)^{1a,2} in which the tetraisopropoxoaluminate ligand is bidentedly (η^2) bonded to zirconium(IV). The Zr^{IV} , which has $4d^05s^0$ electron configuration in the valence shell is relatively large, highly charged, and spherical, with no partly filled shell to give it stereochemical preferences. Consequently, zirconium(IV) compounds exhibit the tendency to achieve higher coordination numbers and a great variety of polyhedra³. Our continued interest in the advancement of coordination chemistry of metals derived from alkoxometallate ligands^{1,4} has prompted us to investigate the chemistry and spectroscopy of targeted heterometallic isopropoxides of zirconium(IV), in which six-, seven- and higher-coordination geometries can be envisaged on the basis of well established ligating modes of the concerned isopropoxometallate ligands¹ such as $\text{M}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9^-$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ti}$, Zr , Sn) and $\text{M}(\text{OPr}^i)_4^-$ ($\text{M} = \text{Al}$, Sb). These types of compounds assume additional importance, due to the possi-

bility of their utilization as potential precursors⁷, for the preparation of useful mixed-metal oxide ceramic materials^{1a,b}. We, therefore, report in this paper, the synthesis and characterization of five new types of heterometallic isopropoxide coordination systems based on tetravalent zirconium center.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Five different types of heterometallic isopropoxide coordination systems featuring zirconium(IV) have been prepared by salt-elimination reactions in benzene medium, using appropriate reactants (ZrCl_4 or a preformed isopropoxometallate complex of zirconium(IV) and desired potassium isopropoxometallate) in required molar ratios as depicted by the following eqs. (1)-(4) :

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The complexes (1)-(5) are highly moisture-sensitive colourless or dusty semisolids or viscous liquids (when freshly prepared), soluble in organic solvents such as PhH, PhMe, CCl₄, CH₂Cl₂ and depict monomeric nature ebullioscopically/cryoscopically in benzene solution (Table 1).

Spectral studies :

The derivatives (1)-(5) exhibit infrared absorptions characteristic of metal attached organic groups^{1a,5} in the regions (in cm⁻¹) : 1165–1160 and 1150–1115 ν(OPrⁱ), 1097–1027 (terminal OPrⁱ), 1015–1000 (bridging OPrⁱ). The metal-oxygen stretching mode appeared in the region 611–515 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR spectra (Table 2) of (1)-(5) exhibit⁶ two dou-

plets in the regions (δ, ppm) : 1.18–1.35 and 1.41–1.51 for terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups, respectively. Signals due to methine protons appear as two broad peaks in the regions 3.99–4.74 and 4.44–4.87, which is consistent with the presence of isopropoxy fragments in terminal and bridging environments.

²⁷Al NMR spectrum of (5) shows broad signal centered at δ 53.6, which is supporting the presence of aluminium in a tetrahedral environment⁷.

The appearance of a sharp ¹¹⁹Sn NMR signal at δ –596 for the derivative (1) is supportive for an octahedral geometry of tin(IV) and the presence of Sn₂(OPrⁱ)₉⁻ moiety⁶.

The structural formulations depicted in the text are based on X-ray crystallographically established ligating modes of the concerned isopropoxometallate ligands¹, such as {Al(OPrⁱ)₄}⁻, {Sb(OPrⁱ)₄}⁻ and {M₂(OPrⁱ)₉}⁻ (M = Sn, Ti, or Zr).

Experimental

All experiments were carried out under rigorous anhydrous conditions, using oven dried (130–140 °C) quick-fit glass apparatus with interchangeable joints, which were cooled either in a desiccator filled with fused CaCl₂ or by adequately protecting them from atmospheric moisture

Table 1. Analytical and some physical data for complexes (1)-(5)

Complex ^a Empirical formula Colour and state ^b	Analysis (%) :						Mol. wt. ^c Found (Calcd.)
	Found (Calcd.)						
	C	H	Cl	Zr	M ^d	OPr ⁱ	
(1)	33.50	6.52	11.04	9.48	24.50	55.10	960
C ₂₇ H ₆₃ Cl ₃ O ₉ Sn ₂ Zr	(33.54)	(6.57)	(11.00)	(9.44)	(24.56) Sn	(55.00)	(966.8)
(2)	39.28	7.67	12.90	11.00	11.56	64.30	820
C ₂₇ H ₆₃ Cl ₃ O ₉ Ti ₂ Zr	(39.30)	(7.70)	(12.89)	(11.06)	(11.60) Ti	(64.45)	(825.1)
(3)	32.78	6.41	8.12	10.32	27.68	53.78	875
C ₂₄ H ₅₆ Cl ₂ Sb ₂ O ₈ Zr	(32.82)	(6.43)	(8.07)	(10.39)	(27.72) Sb	(53.82)	(878.3)
(4)	41.69	8.78	13.62	11.70	6.08	68.2	775
C ₂₇ H ₆₃ Cl ₃ O ₉ TiZr	(41.72)	(8.82)	(13.68)	(11.74)	(6.16) Ti	(68.42)	(777.2)
(5)	46.56	9.08	7.01	9.12	2.64 Al/4.72 Ti	76.35	1008
C ₃₉ H ₉₁ AlCl ₂ O ₁₃ TiZr	(46.60)	(9.13)	(7.05)	(9.08)	(2.68) Al (4.76) Ti	(76.43)	(1005.1)

^aComplex number in parenthesis.

^bAll are colourless semi (or waxy) solids, except (3) which is colourless viscous liquid.

^cDetermined ebullioscopically in benzene using a Gallenkamp ebulliometer with thermister sensing device or cryoscopically in benzene.

^dM = Sb, Al, Ti.

Table 2. NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) for compounds (1)-(5)

Compd.	^1H	$^{27}\text{Al}/^{119}\text{Sn}$
(1)	1.18 (24H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _t ,	-596 (^{119}Sn)
	1.41 (30H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _b ,	
	3.99 (4H, br, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	4.77 (5H, br, OCHMe_2) _b	
(2)	1.34 (24H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	1.51 (30H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _b ,	
	4.74 (4H, br, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	4.87 (5H, br, OCHMe_2) _b	
(3)	1.18 (24H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	1.35 (24H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _b ,	
	4.00 (4H, br, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	4.54 (4H, br, OCHMe_2) _b	
(4)	1.28 (24H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	1.49 (30H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _b ,	
	4.06 (4H, br, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	4.49 (5H, br, OCHMe_2) _b	
(5)	1.26 (42H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _t ,	53.59 (^{27}Al)
	1.52 (36H, d, J 6.2 Hz, OCHMe_2) _b ,	
	4.08 (7H, br, OCHMe_2) _t ,	
	4.50 (6H, br, OCHMe_2) _b	

Abbreviations : d = doublet; br = broad; t = terminal; b = bridging (μ_2 and μ_3).

with guard- and side-tubes filled with self-indicating silica gel.

Solvents were dried and purified by the literature methods^{4b,c}. Isopropoxides of aluminium⁸, titanium⁹, zirconium¹⁰, antimony(III)¹¹ and potassium isopropoxometallates : $\text{KTi}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ ¹² and $\text{KZr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ ¹³, $\text{KSn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ ¹⁴, $\text{KAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ ¹⁵ and $\text{KSb}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ ¹⁶, were prepared according to the procedures described in the literature. $\text{KTiZr}(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ was prepared by equimolar reaction of KOPr^i , $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ in refluxing benzene, followed by removal of the solvent under reduced pressure.

Tin and titanium were estimated as their oxides¹⁷, after digesting the hydrolysed product with concentrated nitric acid. Zirconium and aluminium were determined¹⁷, respectively by mandelate and oxinate methods. Chloride was determined by Volhard's method¹⁷. Isopropoxy groups were estimated by an oxidimetric method¹⁸ using 1 N $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution in 12.5% H_2SO_4 as an oxidant. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically, using Gallenkamp ebulliometer with thermister sensing

device or cryoscopically in benzene solution. Microelemental (C, H) analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400-11 CHNS/O analyzer of this department.

NMR (^1H , ^{27}Al and ^{119}Sn) spectra were recorded on a JEOL AL 300 FTNMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 solution. IR spectra ($4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded as Nujol mulls using CsI optics on a Nicolet Magna-550 spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of $[\text{ZrCl}_3\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}]$ (2) :

To a benzene (50 cm^3) suspension of ZrCl_4 (0.82 g, 3.51 mmol) was added $\text{KTi}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9$ [freshly prepared from K (0.14 g, 3.58 mgatom) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ (2.01 g, 7.07 mmol)] and the resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 5 h, followed by refluxing for 1 h. The precipitated KCl was removed by filtration. Removal of volatile components from the filtrate under reduced pressure, followed by washing the resulting mass by cold ($-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) *n*-hexane, gave analytically pure compound (2) in (2.40 g, 82.8%) yield as colourless semisolid.

Using a procedure similar to (2), the complexes (1), (3) and (4) were prepared by the interactions of ZrCl_4 with $\text{K}\{\text{Sn}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}$, $\text{K}\{\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}$ and $\text{K}\{\text{TiZr}(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}$ in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 molar ratios, respectively. Equimolar reaction of (4) with $\text{K}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}$ yielded the compound (5).

Conclusion and comment

Five different types of heterometallic isopropoxide coordination compounds of zirconium(IV) have been prepared and characterized by elemental analyses, spectroscopic studies and molecular weight measurements. Efforts to develop crystallographically suitable crystals were not successful, mainly due to the nature of the compounds, such inherent difficulties in the X-ray crystallographic structural elucidation of heterometallic alkoxides containing large number of isopropoxy groups have also been experienced by renowned researchers in this field, such as Bradley¹⁹, Caulton and Pfalzgraf²⁰.

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